

COMPARATIVE CLASSIFICATION OF COMPOUND SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION. This article analyzes the Uzbek translation of the English joint sentence. Language also coexists with society, conveys changes and innovations in its life quickly and clearly, has a strong impact on their consciousness, spirituality. Compound sentences make a special contribution to the formation of language.

KEY WORDS: English, Uzbek, compound sentences, means, sentence structure, complex, among young people;

INTRODUCTION

Language is a means of communication between people, through which people express their thoughts, goals, emotions, and communicate and interact. Thoughts can be expressed in different ways: simple or compound sentences, complex compound sentences, two or one-sentence sentences, complete or incomplete sentences.

MAIN PART

Nowadays, at a time when international dialogue and relations are open, translations of English compound sentences are developing. Proof of this is the fact that the words of English phrases enter the Uzbek and other languages. Learning English is a topical issue for young people in Uzbekistan today.

Syntactic units, which are the object of examination of compound sentences and provide a very valuable and interesting material, providing step-by-step with the development of life, their translation into English and Uzbek, the object of study of the ulama is currently relevant. When describing a compound sentence, some English scholars have and about the number of cuts, some focus on the number of simple sentences in the compound sentence, and still others combine these two cases. The theory of compound speech in English was fully formed in English normative grammar in the second half of the nineteenth century and has remained unchanged to the present day. There are many similar theories in the grammars of languages belonging to different gods. The theory of simple and compound sentences is no exception, e.g.

He opened the door and saw us.

U eshikni ochdi va bizni ko'rdi.

She stopped, closed her eyes, and pushed the door.

U to'xtadi, ko'zini yumdi va eshikni itardi.

Such cases are the theoretical basis of the doctrine of scientific grammar of the twentieth century, studied by Uzbek scholars. In twentieth-century linguistics, there are traditional and non-traditional definitions of speech. The definition of a compound sentence is often related to the presence of more than one subordinate clause in its structure and imda. Roderick A. Jacobs said of the parts of speech: "Clauses are constructions with one phrase, that bears the subject relation and another constituent, the verb phrase, bearing the predicate relation."

At the same time, general theoretical issues of syntax have been studied in scientific works published in English since the 1990s. In these works there is information about the joint sentence, its types. Compound sentence components, its use in methods, by the 70s, while

researching the flash compound sentence, the main difference was that they were linked according to (Claube). studied according to which content (clause) it was linked to. According to the scholar, some compound sentences are connected by a connecting word according to their function and its meaning is determined, while others do not require such words when connected. A conjunction with the help of conjunctions is a syndicate without a conjunction. But both of these are called compound sentences because they contain more than one composition.

The English scholar Ilish at that time considered the problem of the transition from homogeneous parts to sentences. He said, "I met my relatives and friends would be said to have been" contracted "out of two sentences: I met my relatives, and I met my friends."

While studying one-member sentences, Ilish also revealed that several of them combine to form a compound sentence:

"A different kind of one-member clause is seen in the following compound sentence: A good leap, and perhaps one might clear the narrow terrace and so crash down yet another thirty feet to the sunbaked ground below." (Huxley)

Such statements can be replaced by simple compound sentences, the scientist goes on to say. The meaning is of course equivalent to that of a sentence like it would be enough to make a good leap, etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, when we consider the problem of interpretation and classification of joint sentences in English and Uzbek, we are convinced that the typical type of equal and subordinate clauses is widespread. We also acknowledge that English and Uzbek conjunctions do not differ in content from conjunctions used in other languages.

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